

ON MIXTURES CONTAINING A WEAK AND A STRONG ACID IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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The transport number of the chloride ion in mixtures containing weak acids and hydrochloric acid is found to be greater than in pure hydrochloric acid solution. The experiments also show the complete suppression of the weak acid. An increase in the hydrogen-ion activity was observed in these acid mixtures. Perchloric acid mixtures did not behave in an exactly analogous manner. The chloride-ion activity was smaller than that of hydrochloric acid alone. The observed results are explained on the assumption of changes in the homogeneity of the solution due to aggregation of water molecules around the suppressed weak acid.

Chemical combination between acids in dilute aqueous solution could be exemplified by the well known class of heteropoly acids. However, interaction between acids in aqueous solutions ceases in most cases at the stage of the suppression of ionisation of the weak acid. Thus, Meyer and Pauletta (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 551) examined the interaction between phosphoric acid on the one hand and hydrochloric or sulphuric acid on the other. They found that although the measured specific conductances were smaller than the additive values, yet they were not smaller than those of the strong acid alone. Kendall and Andrews (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1545) studied the solubility of weak acids in aqueous solutions of strong acids. They showed that a weak acid can behave as a "base" in the presence of a strong acid, the stability of the resulting "salt" being dependent upon the difference in their acid strength. However, Cranston and Duncan (*J. Roy. Tech. Coll.*, 1927, 4, 41) made a study of the changes in p_H and electrical conductance accompanying the replacement of water in hydrochloric acid solutions by acetic, citric, tartaric and phosphoric acids. They noticed that with the increase in the concentration of the weak acid, the specific conductance decreased, but the hydrogen-ion concentration increased. This investigation was extended by Cranston and Brown (*ibid.*, 1936, 13, 569) who noticed a decrease in p_H accompanied by a decrease in the specific conductance in phosphoric-hydrochloric acid solutions. They attribute this behaviour to the fact that the hydrogen electrode can respond in aqueous solutions to any ions in which protons are loosely held. The equilibrium conditions for the reaction between phosphoric and hydrofluoric acid in aqueous solution were studied by Lunge (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 214, 44). The reaction was represented by the following equation :

The equilibrium was shifted to the right by the addition of strong acids, which brought a dehydrating effect.

In the present investigation aqueous solutions of the weak acids, phosphoric, arsenic, acetic and boric acids, were mixed with hydrochloric or perchloric acid. If suppression of ionisation of the weak acid takes place with the formation of an ion-pair, the question which presents itself is whether complex formation between the two acids is due to triple-ion formation in Fuoss' sense. If no compound formation is favoured in these solutions because of the high tendency of the proton to combine with water molecules, one would expect changes in the activities of the free ions brought about by the presence of the suppressed weak acid. However, as will be seen later, triple-ion formation does not occur and that the weak acid behaves as a non-electrolyte.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid were prepared by diluting by weight the constant boiling acid. A stock of exactly 1.0*N* solution was prepared and its strength was adjusted by standardisation against pure anhydrous sodium carbonate and checked gravimetrically as silver chloride.

Perchloric acid solutions were obtained by diluting a 60% A. R. sample with conductivity water. The solutions were standardised against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution. Phosphoric acid solution was prepared by dissolving a pure sample of phosphorus pentoxide in conductivity water. The strength of the solution was determined gravimetrically as magnesium pyrophosphate

Arsenic acid solution was obtained by dissolving crystals having the composition $\text{As}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in conductivity water. These crystals were obtained by the repeated digestion of pure arsenic trioxide with nitric acid on a water-bath. By dissolving the mass in water and evaporating, white crystalline solid was formed which was recrystallised from conductivity water. The solution of arsenic acid was standardised gravimetrically as magnesium pyro-arsenate.

Acetic acid solution was obtained from pure glacial acetic acid. The solution was standardised by titration against standard sodium hydroxide solution. Boric acid solution was obtained by dissolving the necessary weight of the A. R. sample in conductivity water to give a stock of 1.0*N* solution. Conductivity water used in these experiments had a specific conductance of 1.5×10^{-6} mhos.

Transport Number.—An apparatus similar to that of Lottermoser and Fritsche (*Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 80, 166) was used. It had a uniform bore of 1.5 cm. and was provided with a large stop-cock having the same bore separating the anode from the middle compartment. A lightly amal-

gamated cadmium rod served as the anode ; as cathode, mercury covered with a half saturated solution of cadmium nitrate was used. The current was measured by a silver coulometer containing 20% silver nitrate solution. The apparatus was checked by carrying out experiments on a 0.05*N*-KCl; the average value of 0.498 was obtained for the transport number of the K⁺ ion, which is in close agreement with the accepted value of McInnes and Dole (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1357).

Potentiometric Measurements.—The p_H value of the solutions was measured by means of the quinhydrone electrode with a saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrode. A saturated KCl-agar bridge was used to eliminate liquid junction potentials. The potential of the cells attained an equilibrium value at 25° after 5 to 15 minutes, and were reproducible to less than one millivolt. The p_{Cl} measurements were made by a silver-silver chloride electrode prepared according to the directions of McInnes and Parker (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 1445). The electrodes were tested before use in solutions of hydrochloric acid of known activities. The reference electrode was a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by an ammonium nitrate-agar bridge.

The solutions examined were always 0.24*N* with respect to the weak acid and 0.08*N*, 0.12*N*, 0.24*N*, 0.48*N* and 0.72*N* with respect to the strong acid. For reference these solutions will be designated by the ratio of the weak acid to the strong acid in a given solution.

DISCUSSION

Transport Number.—Measurements on mixtures of phosphoric with either hydrochloric or perchloric acid were carried out as a guide to detect the nature of the ionic species in solution. These mixtures were chosen because of the readiness with which the change in concentration in the electrode compartments could be made by gravimetric methods. Table I shows the results of experiments with phosphoric and hydrochloric acids in the ratios 1:2 and 1:3. They represent the average value for a set of five experiments on each ratio. Similar results were obtained with phosphoric and perchloric acid mixtures in the same ratios. These experiments indicate that phosphoric acid does not move in the electric current, thus behaving as a non-electrolyte. They also indicate that phosphoric acid in aqueous solution cannot behave as a "base", and thus triple-ion formation cannot be favoured in such aqueous solutions. However, in non-aqueous solutions (unpublished data by the author) where the solvent can act as a weak base as compared to water, triple-ion formation was found to occur. It is to be noticed that the transport number of the

Cl-ion has increased considerably in these aqueous acid mixtures over that in pure hydrochloric acid solution.

TABLE I
Transport number experiments on phosphoric-hydrochloric acid system at 25°.

	1 : 2 Ratio 10 volts 70 m.amps.	1 : 3 20 volts 100 m.amps.
Original solution.		
Wt. of 20 c.c. of solution	20.1206	20.2982 g.
HCl in 20 c.c.	0.3458	0.5430
H ₃ PO ₄ in 20 c.c.	0.1594	0.1575
Mg ₃ P ₂ O ₇ per 20 c.c.	0.1790	0.1788
H ₂ O in 20 c.c.	19.615	19.598
Anode solution.		
Wt. of anode solution	61.74 g.	83.68 g.
20 c.c. anode solution	20.140	20.303
HCl in anode solution	0.997	2.225
H ₃ PO ₄ in " "	0.489	0.649
Cd Cl ₂ in " "	0.188	0.203
H ₂ O " " "	60.07	80.80
Mg ₃ P ₂ O ₇ per 20 c.c.	0.1807	0.1795
Silver deposited	0.2235	0.2384
T _{Cl} -	0.822	0.660

International Critical Tables, Vol. VI, 1929 Edition gives :

T_{Cl}- in 0.500N-HCl=0.160 at 18°C

T_{Cl} in 1.00N-HCl=0.156 at 18°C

Potentiometric Measurements: (i) Measurements of the Hydrogen-ion Activity.—The results of these measurements are shown in Table II. For the sake of comparison the p_H values of the different acid mixtures are given together with that of the strong acid alone. Table II shows that in all cases the acid mixtures are more acid than the strong acid alone. With the exception of the arsenic-hydrochloric acid mixtures in the ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3, the p_H values decrease in the direction : phosphoric to boric acid mixtures. Measurements with perchloric acid may also reveal the fact whether the observed deviations are dependent on the nature of the strong acid added. Table III shows the p_H values of the acid mixtures with perchloric acid as the strong acid. The weak acid-perchloric acid mixtures behave in a manner which is completely different from the corresponding mixtures containing hydrochloric acid. Thus, arsenic and acetic acid mixtures possess

p_H values which are always greater than those of perchloric acid alone. Boric acid mixtures are more acid than perchloric acid and in this respect they behave similar to the hydrochloric acid mixtures, but the individual values of p_H are higher in the ratios 3:1, 2:1, 1:1 and 1:3 and smaller in the ratio 1:2 than the corresponding hydrochloric acid mixtures. Phosphoric-perchloric acid mixtures, however, show p_H values which are smaller than those of perchloric acid as the concentration of perchloric acid is increased up to the ratio 1:1.

TABLE II

Comparison of the p_H values of the acid mixtures containing hydrochloric acid.

Ratio.	p_H (HCl)	p_H (H_3PO_4 + HCl)	p_H (H_3AsO_4 + HCl)	p_H (AcOH + HCl)	p_H (H_3BO_3 + HCl)
3:1	1.18	0.961	0.896	0.446	0.449
2:1	1.02	0.787	0.732	0.379	0.348
1:1	0.730	0.515	0.611	0.280	0.281
1:2	0.430	0.174	0.251	0.099	0.181
1:3	0.230	0.075	0.195	0.017	0.017

TABLE III

Comparison of the p_H values of the acid mixtures containing perchloric acid.

Ratio.	p_H $HClO_4$	p_H ($HClO_4$ + H_3PO_4)	p_H (H_3AsO_4 + $HClO_4$)	p_H (AcOH + $HClO_4$)	p_H (H_3BO_3 + $HClO_4$)
3:1	1.020	0.790	1.073	1.135	0.925
2:1	0.832	0.652	0.936	0.965	0.740
1:1	0.529	0.374	0.623	0.661	0.404
1:2	0.250	0.331	0.360	0.331	0.123
1:3	0.119	0.281	0.240	0.179	0.109

With increasing concentration of perchloric acid, the p_H values are greater than those of perchloric acid alone. Thus, the nature of the strong acid added to the weak acid is an important factor in bringing physical changes in the properties of the acid mixtures. The above results, with the quinhydrone electrode, were also checked with the glass electrode with mean deviations of ± 0.03 of a p_H unit.

(ii) *Measurement of the Chlorine-ion Activity.*—Table IV shows the results obtained with the silver-silver chloride electrode and checked with an apparatus similar to that of Guntelberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 123, 199) which consisted of a cell without liquid junction and provided with hydrogen and silver-silver chloride electrodes. This procedure eliminated the possibility of errors in the observed potentials which might be introduced on account of the liquid junction potentials. On considering the figures in Table IV it can be seen that the p_{Cl} values of the acid mixtures are always higher than those of hydrochloric acid by 0.2 to 0.4 of a p_{Cl} unit. The presence of suppressed weak acid alters the ionic activities of the strong acid.

TABLE IV

Comparison of the p_{Cl} values of the acid mixtures containing hydrochloric acid.

Ratio.	p_{Cl} (HCl)	p_{Cl} ($H_3PO_4 +$ HCl)	p_{Cl} ($H_3AsO_4 +$ HCl)	p_{Cl} (AcOH + HCl)	p_{Cl} ($H_3BO_3 +$ HCl)
3 : 1	1.20	1.53	1.67	1.44	1.46
2 : 1	1.02	1.26	1.45	1.31	1.33
1 : 1	0.75	0.96	1.19	1.02	1.09
1 : 2	0.44	0.63	0.89	0.82	0.76
1 : 3	0.23	0.53	0.60	0.55	0.59

The effect of non-electrolytes, such as sucrose, on the electrical conductance and concentration of hydrogen ion in aqueous hydrochloric acid solutions was investigated by Zhukov and Dneprov (*J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1940, 10, 291). The transport number of the chloride remained constant in solutions containing sucrose up to 30% by weight. The activity of the hydrogen ions increased with increase in sucrose content. Thus, the p_H value of a solution containing 1% sucrose changed from 1.14 to 0.38. Similar experiments by Fischer and Koval (*Univ. Kiev Bull. Sci. Rec. Chim.*, 1939, 4, 137) showed that sucrose, acetone and urea reduced the transport number of the hydrogen ion in solutions of sulphuric acid. They concluded that complex ions of the type (H_3O^+ , non-electrolyte) existed. Their reference substance was accordingly not stationary in the electric current. However, Bartlett and Daubin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1939) observed an increase in the acid strength of hydrogen chloride by the addition of phenol in dioxane as a solvent. They attributed the effect to be due to hydrogen bond formation.

Hydrogen bond formation between the suppressed weak acid and the chloride ion would account for the high acidity observed in these acid

mixtures, but fails to explain the high value of the transport number of the chloride ion. If the suppressed weak acid is assumed to be present as an ion-pair, the high polarity of the latter would orient water molecules around it. The solution would therefore exhibit a deficiency in water molecules in regions containing chloride ions. This "dehydration" effect would render the chloride ion more mobile and the solution would show a local decrease in the concentration of hydrated chloride ions. Thermal agitation in solution does not seem to alter this picture where the homogeneity of the solution is disturbed in the vicinity of the ion-pair weak acid. The existence of definite hydrates of sucrose in aqueous solution, has been recently confirmed by X-rays by Young and Jones (*J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1949, 53, 1334). The increase in the acidity of the strong acid could be explained on the basis of a deformation brought in by the presence of the large field of the ion-pair tending to separate the hydrogen ion to a larger distance. Even if we assume that the weak acid is present in the co-valent form, one should expect congregation of water molecules to occur on account of induced polarity in the acid by the highly polar solvent molecules. The deformation of hydrogen chloride due to external fields has been confirmed by infra-red measurements (Williams, *Phys. Rev.*, 1936, 50, 719) and Raman spectroscopy (West and Arthur, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5 10).

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